

Separation of Bi(III) by Anion-Exchange Chromatography in Maleate and Succinate Solutions[†]

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Systematic studies on the anion-exchange behaviour of Bi(III) in maleic acid and succinic acid solutions on Amberlite IRA-401 are carried out. Sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids at different concentrations were tried as eluants in the two systems. Their efficiency being evaluated in terms of distribution coefficients. Methods have been developed for the separation of Bi(III) from several elements in maleate as well as in succinate media with the technique of selective sorption or selective elution. Methods are applied to the analysis of Wood's metal. Separations are also worked out with liquid anion-exchanger, Amberlite LA-I in xylene.

ION-EXCHANGE behaviour of Bi(III) has been extensively studied in mineral acid media as both anionic and cationic complex¹⁻³. However, in carboxylic acid media the studies are mainly confined to cation exchange separations^{4,5}. Although for anion exchange separations, limited use has been made of EDTA⁶, oxalate^{7,8} and formate⁹, no work has been reported on the ion-exchange behaviour of Bi(III) in maleic acid and succinic acid solutions. Present work relates to the systematic study of the ion-exchange separation of Bi(III) on Amberlite IRA-401 from several elements in maleate and succinate media. Liquid anion-exchanger, Amberlite LA-I, is also used for the separation of Bi(III) from various elements.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: An anion-exchange column (1×7 cm) was used. A Toshniwal pH meter was used for pH measurements.

A stock solution of Bi(III) was prepared by dissolving 1.16 g of A. R. bismuth nitrate penta-

hydrate in dilute nitric acid and making up to 500 ml with double distilled water. The solution on standardisation volumetrically¹⁰ with EDTA contained 0.93 mg ml⁻¹ of Bi(III).

EDTA (0.01 M) was prepared in double distilled water. The ion-exchangers used are Amberlite IRA-401 (Cl⁻) and Amberlite LA-I (both from Rohm and Hass Company, Philadelphia, U.S.A.). The resin was converted to the appropriate form by equilibrating for 6 hrs. with a 2% solution of maleic acid or succinic acid. The resin was then washed free of the excess acid using double distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Ion-exchange studies in maleate and succinate media: The distribution coefficients (K_d values) of Bi(III) and other related metals like Pd²⁺, Cd²⁺, In³⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Th⁴⁺, etc., were determined by equilibrating 2.5 g of resin (maleate form) with 10 ml of about 1 mg. ml⁻¹ solutions of metals and 20 ml maleic acid at different concentrations. The metal present in the aqueous phase was

TABLE—1. K_d VALUES IN MALEIC AND SUCCINIC ACIDS

Metal	Maleic acid, %					Succinic acid, %				
	0.50	1	2	4	6	0.50	1	2	4	6
Bi	117.60	117.80	119.00	118.00	118.00	146.90	146.00	196.00	140.00	140.20
Th	0.60	0.60	0.62	0.61	0.61	75.40	38.40	17.60	4.50	7.90
Fe	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.45	0.62	0.62	0.43	0.45
Pb	0.77	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.25	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29
Zn	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
Cd	1.16	1.60	1.80	1.80	1.60	0.59	0.59	0.50	0.59	0.50
Co	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.58	0.58
Ni	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.60
In	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
Mg	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
Mn	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.10	0.10	0.36	0.36	0.89	0.39	0.39

N.A = No Absorption.

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determined volumetrically by EDTA¹¹. K_d values are calculated and results given in Table 1.

K_d values of metals in succinic acid was also determined in a similar manner by taking the succinate form of the resin. Sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids at different concentrations were tested as eluants, their efficiency being evaluated in terms of distribution coefficients which are given in Table 2.

In maleic acid, as seen from Table 1, there is a large difference in the K_d values between Bi(III) and other metals thereby indicating the possibilities of good separation of Bi(III) from other metals. For the elution of Bi(III) from the resin, various eluants were tried. The anionic maleate complex of Bi(III) was sorbed on the column. After washing the column with 20 ml distilled water, Bi(III) was eluted with various eluants. Collected 10 ml fractions of the effluent and analysed for the metal content using EDTA.

The elution constant (E) and the volume distribution coefficient (D_v) were calculated¹² from the peak elution volume (V_{max}) and total volume of the eluants (Vt). The results are shown in Table 3. On

the basis of the results, the eluants can be arranged in the order of increasing efficiency as follows :

Ammonium sulphate, ammonium chloride and sodium chloride are found to be poor eluants.

In succinic acid medium (Table 1) both Bi(III) and Th(IV) show considerable sorption and these two can be separated from each other by selective elution by mineral acids ; while all other metals are sorbed very little and can be separated by selective sorption.

Elution studies of the anionic succinate complex of Bi(III) was done as described for maleic acid complex and the results are incorporated in Table 3. Here also eluants showed nearly the same order of increasing efficiency

Other eluants such as ammonium sulphate, ammonium chloride and sodium nitrate do not elute satisfactorily.

Separation in maleate medium : The separation of Bi(III) from Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , In^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} ,

 TABLE-2: K_d VALUES IN NITRIC, PERCHLORIC AND SULPHURIC ACIDS

Metal	Nitric acid			Perchloric acid			Sulphuric acid		
	1N	2N	3N	1N	2N	3N	1N	2N	3N
Th	0.97	0.37	0.97	N.A	N.A	N.A	5.02	5.07	5.08
Fe	N.A	N.A	N.A	1.88	2.52	2.52	1.08	1.08	1.08
Bi	92.10	92.00	92.00	10.79	6.99	5.14	N.A	N.A	N.A
Pb	0.77	0.77	0.77	N.A	N.A	N.A	2.87	2.90	2.87
Zn	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
Cd	8.36	8.36	8.36	5.45	5.40	5.45	N.A	N.A	N.A
Co	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	0.18	0.20	0.18
Ni	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
In	0.03	0.03	0.01	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
Tl	0.14	0.14	0.14	N.A	N.A	N.A	0.17	0.16	0.16
Mg	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	0.18	N.A	N.A	N.A
Mn	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.91	0.87

N.A = No absorption

TABLE-3: ANION-EXCHANGE STUDIES OF BISMUTH

Eluant	Concentration N	Peak elution volume V_{max}		Total volume of eluant Vt		%Recovery		Elution constant E		Volume distribution coefficient D_v	
		Maleic	Succinic	Maleic	Succinic	Maleic	Succinic	Maleic	Succinic	Maleic	Succinic
H_2SO_4	1.0	20	20	50	50	100.00	100.00	0.08	0.08	4.09	4.09
	2.0	20	10	40	40	100.00	100.00	0.10	0.10	4.09	2.04
	3.0	10	10	20	20	100.00	100.00	0.19	0.19	1.54	2.04
HNO_3	1.0	--	--	120	200	55.00	54.00	0.03	0.02	--	--
	2.0	50	60	80	180	58.50	58.80	0.04	0.03	11.74	--
	3.0	40	--	60	120	60.50	60.00	0.06	0.03	10.10	--
HCl	1.0	--	--	150	150	62.50	60.00	0.03	0.03	--	--
	2.0	--	--	120	120	64.00	64.50	0.03	0.03	--	--
	3.0	60	50	110	80	65.00	70.50	0.04	0.05	7.64	14.79
HClO_4	1.0	50	--	80	120	78.40	70.80	0.04	0.03	11.74	--
	2.0	30	60	60	80	80.60	72.20	0.06	0.05	7.64	14.79
	3.0	20	30	50	60	84.00	84.00	0.07	0.06	4.09	7.64
NaNO_3	1.0	--	--	160	--	56.50	--	0.03	--	--	--
	2.0	--	--	140	--	58.00	--	0.03	--	--	--
	3.0	--	--	130	150	60.10	54.60	0.03	0.03	--	--
NaClO_4	1.0	--	--	200	--	65.00	--	0.02	--	--	--
	2.0	--	--	150	200	70.80	65.00	0.03	0.02	--	--
	3.0	--	--	120	150	74.50	72.00	0.03	0.03	--	--

Fe^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Th^{4+} was based on selective sorption. Bi(III) forms strong anionic maleate complex at pH 2-3 and it is absorbed in the column; while other metals are not retained on the column when sorbed along with Bi(III) .

Binary mixtures of Bi(III) with other metals containing sufficient amount of maleic acid (2%) was loaded on a column of anion exchange resin (2.5 g). The solution was recycled thrice at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} and was kept for 30 min. The effluent was collected and the resin washed with some distilled water and Bi(III) was then eluted with $2N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The results are given in Table 4.

TABLE-4

SEPARATION OF Bi(III) IN MALEATE AND SUCCINATE, MEDIA, $\text{Bi(III)}=9.3 \text{ MG}$

Foreign ion	Amount added	Maleate medium		Succinate medium	
		Bi recovered mg	Per cent. recovery, %	Bi recovered mg	Per cent. recovery, %
Th	7.56	9.30	100.00	9.30	100.00
In	9.59	9.30	100.00	9.30	100.00
Zn	8.40	9.30	100.00	9.00	99.17
Fe(III)	7.42	8.74	94.60	9.30	100.00
Ni	7.00	9.15	99.00	9.30	100.00
Co	7.00	9.30	100.00	8.70	98.54
Mn	7.00	9.30	100.00	9.30	100.00
Mg	6.86	9.82	105.00	Precipitation	
Pb	6.83	9.30	100.00	8.70	93.54
Cd	7.70	9.30	100.00	8.40	90.40

A similar separation was possible using the liquid anion-exchanger, Amberlite LA-1 (Table 5). A few

TABLE-5

LIQUID ANION-EXCHANGE SEPARATION OF Bi(III) IN MALEATE AND SUCCINATE MEDIUM, $\text{Bi}=5.40 \text{ MG}$

Foreign ion	Amount added, mg	Maleate medium		Succinate medium	
		Bi recovered mg	Per cent. recovery %	Bi recovered mg	Per cent. recovery %
Th	3.20	5.40	100.00	5.40	100.00
In	4.13	5.40	100.00	5.40	100.00
Ni	3.00	5.40	100.00	5.40	100.00
Co	3.00	5.20	96.29	5.40	100.00
Mn	3.00	5.20	98.15	5.29	98.29
Mg	2.95	5.20	96.29	5.20	96.29
Pb	2.93	5.40	100.00	5.00	92.50
Cd	3.30	5.40	100.00	4.40	90.74
Zn	3.60	5.40	100.00	5.00	92.50
Fe	3.06	5.20	96.29	5.20	96.29

drops of $1M \text{ NH}_4\text{Cl}$ was added to the aqueous phase for clear separation of layers. For experimental work 15 ml of 2% maleic acid (or succinic acid) and 20 ml of 10% Amberlite LA-1 in xylene were used. Bi(III) was back-extracted from the organic phase using two 10 ml portions of $2N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

Separation in succinate medium: These separations are based upon the processes of selective sorption and selective elution. Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} ,

Mg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and In^{3+} do not form anionic succinate complexes and therefore are not retained on the column when sorbed along with Bi(III) and hence can be separated by selective sorption. A 0.5-1% solution of succinic acid was used. Results are given in Table 4.

It was observed that Th^{4+} also forms a reasonably strong complex with succinic acid and is absorbed on the resin under the experimental conditions. However, it can be eluted before Bi(III) with $1N \text{ HNO}_3$ by selective elution.

Similar separations are possible using liquid anion-exchanger, Amberlite LA-1 (Table 5). For a clear separation of layers 2 ml of 1% solution of NH_4Cl or $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ is added. A 0.5-1% solution of succinic acid and 10% Amberlite LA-1 in xylene are used.

Application to analysis of Wood's Metal: The sample of Wood's metal (0.02 g) is dissolved in a few drops of conc. HNO_3 and diluted to 10 ml. Added 20 ml of 2% maleic acid and pH is adjusted between 2 and 3. The mixture is sorbed on the column of anion-exchanger (2.5 g). After flushing the column with water, Bi(III) is eluted with $2N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and determined as described earlier. Analysis is also carried out using the liquid anion-exchanger. The results are given in Table 6.

TABLE-6

ANALYSIS OF WOOD'S METAL

Method	Bi(III) found*	Reported value (BDH sample)
Amberlite IRA-401	48.60%	50%
Amberlite LA-1	49.30%	

* Average of two experiments

Thus, the method is quite useful and convenient for the separation of Bi(III) from other related metals. The added advantage is that both maleic acid and succinic acid do not interfere in the complexometric titrations with EDTA. The method is recommended for the determination of Bi(III) in alloys.

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